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Leveraging Mechatronic Systems for Organizational Management: A Knowledge Management Approach in the Automotive Industry

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Abstract: *Organizational management in the automotive industry can be characterized by the integration of mechatronic systems to improve overall efficiency, safety and performance. This study aims to explore how advanced mechatronic systems revolutionize the industry but also how they can be a component of knowledge management in the automotive industry. The integration of mechatronic systems in the automotive industry not only brings high performance but also strengthens the management strategy, ensuring continuous adaptation to market requirements. Thus, the current work tries to identify the value of mechatronic systems as components of organizational management or better said, it can be seen as an approach to knowledge management in the automotive industry*

Keywords: *Research; Mechatronic Systems; Development; Innovation*

1. Introduction

In the contemporary era of advanced technology, the concept of mechatronics represents a revolutionary paradigm in the development of intelligent products and systems. With roots in three major fields—mechanics, electronics, and computer science—mechatronics redefines traditional concepts by bringing a synergistic integration of these seemingly distinct disciplines. This close interdependence in mechatronics paves the way for exceptional innovations and complex systems that have the potential to fundamentally transform the way humans interact with the technological world.

Onwubolu defines the concept as the interdisciplinary field that connects mechanical engineering, electrical and electronic engineering, and computer science, known as MECHATRONICS (Onwubolu, 2005). This concept originated in Japan in the eighth decade of the last century. The term "MECHATRONICS" was patented by the Yaskawa Electric Corporation and was used to describe the technological fusion between mechanics, electronics, and computer science. Practically, anything that can be called a "high-tech product" is a mechatronic product. Thus, mechatronics aims to exploit the action domains of mechanics, electronics, and computer science to design systems that surpass the known barriers of each field individually. It is important to understand that in mechatronics, the entire

resulting system is more than the sum of its components. The synergistic interactions between mechanics, electronics, and computer science lead to the emergence of innovative entities such as intelligent robots, advanced medical devices, and autonomous vehicles.

To deeply understand mechatronics and how it has become an essential component in modern automobiles, it is important to focus on the evolution of this discipline, as can be seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The technological flow towards mechatronic integration

Initially, mechanical engineering and electrical engineering were separate fields, each with its own principles and methodologies. However, technological advancements have necessitated the development of integrated products, incorporating both mechanical and electronic or electrical components. In response to this demand, mechatronics has emerged as a pivotal development in the organizational management of technological innovation. In the context of modern organizational management, influenced by mechatronic systems, the integration of knowledge from various fields has become essential for optimizing processes and increasing competitiveness (Bâlc, Pop, 2016; Oprean et al., 2011). In the automotive industry, this interdisciplinary approach has been crucial for the development of mechatronic systems that not only enhance performance and safety but also contribute to operational efficiency, essential components of organizations focused on innovation and sustainability (Țițu et al., 2022).

2. Classification of Mechatronic Systems in the Automotive Industry

A new generation of vehicles has emerged within the car manufacturing industry, comprising intelligent vehicles that consist of various mechatronic systems and subsystems, including but not limited to:

- Motor System
- Steering system
- Electronic safety, door opening, and closing system
- Electronic wiper activation system
- Electric lighting system
- Stability control system
- Parking system
- Management and control system
- Braking and brake assistance system.

3. Basic Concepts of the Main Mechatronic Systems in the Automotive Industry

3.1. Motor system

The motor system is the central element of a car, generating the power needed to propel and control the vehicle's movement. It consists of two major categories:

- the internal combustion motor

Figure 2. Internal combustion motor (MDLPL, 2020)

- the electric motor

Figure 3. Electric motors (PLEȘA, 2020)

3.2. Steering system

This system allows the driver to control the direction and maneuver the vehicle. It includes multiple subsystems and technologies working together to ensure precise and safe steering.

Figure 4. Electric motors (autotehnica, 2014)

3.3. Electronic safety, door opening, and closing system

This system is vital for modern vehicles, ensuring safety and passenger control. It involves components and technologies working together to ensure proper functioning of the vehicle's doors.

Figure 5. Central locking system

3.4. Electronic windshield wiper activation system

This system ensures visibility in unfavourable weather conditions and uses technological components for controlling and activating the windshield wipers.

Figure 6. Wiper activation system (Source: Bosch)

3.5. Lighting system

Essential for ensuring visibility at night and in various low-light situations, the lighting system involves complex technologies to provide appropriate illumination without affecting other traffic participants.

Figure 7. Lighting system (Source: Exibitech)

3.6. Stability control system

This system significantly impacts driver and passenger comfort and safety by supporting the wheels, absorbing shocks, and maintaining stability while driving.

Figure 8. Stability control system (Source: autotehnica, 2014)

3.7. Parking system

Designed to enhance the safety and precision of parking manoeuvres, the parking system minimizes the risk of damage and accidents during parking.

Figure 9. Parking system (Source: Kia)

3.8. Management and control system

One of the most complex systems in a vehicle, it supervises and regulates the functioning of various vehicle systems, using a combination of hardware and software components to monitor, coordinate, and control vehicle activity.

Figure 10. Management and control system (Source: SLcontrols)

3.9. Braking system

The braking system is one of the most important systems within a vehicle. It not only facilitates the stopping of the vehicle but is also considered an essential component in road safety. Without it, driving would be an exceptionally difficult and dangerous task, as seen in Figure 11.

Figure 11. Braking system (Source: Continental)

4. The Evolution of Mechatronic Systems in the Automotive Industry

The automotive industry has been transforming remarkably, significantly impacting vehicle technology and how vehicles are developed and produced. This transformation redefines how vehicles are conceived, proposing a transition from viewing cars as mechanical devices with specific electrical controls to perceiving them as complex mechatronic devices.

According to Rolf Isermann, a researcher at the Technical University of Darmstadt, Germany, in his work "Mechatronic Systems—Innovative Products with Embedded Control," the integration of mechanics, electronics, and information processing in mechanical and electrical engineering has become so tight that it has resulted in a new series of integrated systems known as mechatronic systems.

Ten years after the publication of this work, 173 specialized publications referenced it. Some notable titles include "Automotive Control: The State of the Art and Perspective," "Multisensor Fusion and Integration: A Review on Approaches and Its Applications in Mechatronics," and "Beyond Advanced Mechatronics: New Design Challenges of Social-Cyber-Physical Systems."

The widespread use of mechatronics in the automotive industry and other specialized fields raises the question: How did mechatronics advance so rapidly in such a short time, as shown in Figures 12 and 13.

Figure 12. The modern automobile developed in the 19th century (Source: EducationNG)

Figure 13. The modern automobile developed in the 21st century (Source: Continental)

5. Chronological Development of Mechatronic Systems

The development of mechatronic systems involves key areas as illustrated in Figure 14, showing a close link to the construction of autonomous mechanical systems (Bishop, 2002).

Figure 14. Key development domains of mechatronics (Bishop, 2002)

Modeling the physical system has been a critical factor in the development of mechatronics. It allows engineers to create simulations and mathematical models of mechatronic systems. These models help understand system behavior before physical construction, saving and optimizing time and resources.

Signal and system theory provides a mathematical framework for analyzing and controlling mechatronic systems. It enables the development of advanced control systems to manage and regulate the mechanical and electrical components of the systems (Bishop, 2002).

The integration of computer and logic systems is crucial in developing mechatronics. It creates a bridge between humans and systems, allowing for the control and monitoring of systems through various user interfaces (Bishop, 2002).

The development of specific software for mechatronic systems significantly contributes to the rapid spread of these systems in the industry and globally. These programs are developed to translate data received as electrical signals, store these data, and, after thorough analysis, respond according to the system's situation (Bishop, 2002).

For the entire system to become automated, it is necessary to introduce elements capable of independently perceiving external signals, achieved through sensors and actuators.

These elements are key to collecting data from the external environment of the mechatronic system and determining the system's internal state. Developing these precise and accurate elements is essential for the optimal functioning of mechatronic systems (Bishop, 2002).

The advancement of mechatronics is fueled by the intersection and collaboration of diverse fields, including robotics, the automotive industry, industrial automation, and medical equipment. This collaborative effort enables mechatronics to progress by intertwining mechanics with electronics and information science to create intelligent and efficient systems.

6. Technological Innovations and Recent Advances in Mechatronic Systems

In recent decades, there has been a significant transformation in the industrial landscape due to technological innovation and the advancement of mechatronic systems. The former Japanese Society for the Promotion of Machine Industry (JSPMI) classified mechatronic products into four distinct categories:

Class 1: Mechanical Products with Embedded Electronics

Class 2: Modernized Traditional Mechanical Systems

Class 3: Initially Mechanical Systems, but Electrified

Class 4: Synergistic Integration of Mechanical and Electronic Technologies

Class 1 products are known for their use of servo technology, power electronics, and control theory. Class 2 products incorporate computing and memory components, along with circuits with special capabilities. Class 3 products involve the replacement of mechanical systems with integrated circuits and microprocessors. Class 4 products are essentially mechatronic products achieved through the synergistic integration of technologies.

In the automotive industry, these advancements have resulted in significant progress, particularly in the development of systems to enhance safety and ambient facilities. Systems such as ABS, EBD, TCS, VDC, BA, ESP, and ESC have played vital roles in shaping modern vehicles.

7. Effects of Mechatronic Systems Development

Over the past few decades, technological advancements in mechatronics have significantly influenced innovations in sophisticated automobile systems. This has brought about profound changes in the automotive industry, impacting vehicle design, manufacturing, and operation.

Mechatronics-based technological innovations have become indispensable for the progress of this field.

There has been a notable shift in the major systems of vehicles from predominantly mechanical systems with limited electronic control to highly integrated mechatronic systems that rely heavily on electronic control. This shift is primarily driven by the imperative to enhance functional performance, which can only be efficiently achieved through electronic technologies.

The development of mechatronic systems in vehicles has led to improvements in comfort, safety, reliability, driving performance, and reductions in fuel consumption, emissions, and production processes. However, implementing these functions in vehicles has been challenging due to limited available space. (Schoner, 2004).

Mechatronics also aims to reduce costs associated with mechanical parts by integrating them with electronic components and other mechanical construction components. Overall, mechatronics is not just about the simultaneous use of electronics and mechanics; it entails the synergistic use of multiple engineering disciplines, incorporating electronic technologies, actuators, sensors, and communication systems to facilitate improvement and evolution (Tomizuka, 2000).

8. Conclusions

The field of advanced mechatronic systems in vehicles has undergone significant evolution in recent decades, driven by interdisciplinary approaches and technological innovations. This evolution has fundamentally transformed the design, manufacturing, and usage of vehicles. To better understand this complexity, the basic concepts of mechatronic systems in the automotive industry have been identified and developed, encompassing crucial systems such as the engine, steering, braking, management and control, and safety systems, all contributing to the vehicle's integrated functionality.

The chronological development of mechatronic systems reflects a journey from simple mechanisms to complex, interconnected, and interdependent systems. This transformation has been driven by technological innovations, including advanced sensors, artificial intelligence, and vehicle-to-vehicle communication.

Currently, there are multiple technical and technological challenges in developing mechatronic systems. Integrating emerging technologies, such as autonomous vehicles and vehicle-to-vehicle networks, requires innovative solutions to manage complexity and ensure interoperability. These challenges are further complicated by stringent regulations regarding emissions, vehicle safety, and cybersecurity, requiring robust strategies and solutions. Collaboration between industry, governments, and regulatory organizations is essential to establish a coherent and effective framework. Continuous innovations are necessary to meet new requirements and ensure that mechatronic systems in vehicles adapt to rapid technological changes.

Compliance with imposed standards is crucial, as it not only ensures adherence to norms but also promotes common practices in the industry. This consolidation not only solidifies safety and performance standards but also facilitates the global exchange of technology and knowledge between manufacturers.

In conclusion, the current state of knowledge in advanced mechatronic systems in vehicles represents a sophisticated amalgamation of technological advancements, challenges, and innovations. These components are increasingly integrated into the organizational management of companies within the automotive industry. Mechatronic systems serve not only as technological solutions but also as essential components of organizational management strategies. They contribute to process efficiency, continuous innovation, and adaptation to the requirements of the constantly evolving automotive landscape. Therefore, success in this sector is contingent upon organizations' adeptness at integrating mechatronic systems effectively into their management and strategic decision-making processes.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

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